

Morphological and Solidification Studies of the Naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene Eutectic

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The mechanism of eutectic solidification of naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene system has been investigated by spontaneous crystallisation, unidirectional velocity of crystallisation, and microscopic studies. Growth of the two phases of the eutectic occur side by side as controlled by cross-diffusion of the components ahead of the solid liquid interface. Nonideal character of the binary system has been established from the excess thermodynamic functions.

ALTHOUGH the subject of eutectic solidification has been of absorbing interest for many years¹⁻⁵, much of the recent developments in understanding crystal growth has been stimulated by its increasing commercial importance. Most of the work done on two-component systems relate to the systems forming regular eutectic morphologies. The kinetics and morphologies of irregular eutectic structures, however, remain little understood. The present investigation was undertaken to study the solidification of binary organic system made up of naphthalene and *p*-dichlorobenzene which is expected to give faceted-faceted (irregular) crystal morphology.

Experimental

Naphthalene (B.D.H.) was purified by ordinary distillation followed by slow sublimation, m.p. 353.3 K. *p*-Dichlorobenzene (B.D.H.) was purified by repeated distillation (at 447-451 K), m.p. 326.7 K. The experimental techniques for studying the phase diagram, temperature of spontaneous crystallisation, linear velocity of crystallisation and microscopic structures have been described earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

The ideal liquidus temperatures (T) for naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene system at different compositions (x_1^l) were computed from equation (1)⁷ by putting activity coefficient $\gamma_1^l = 1$,

$$-\ln x_1^l \gamma_1^l = \frac{\Delta_f H_1^0}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_1^0} \right) \quad (1)$$

It becomes clear from Fig. 1 that the ideal phase diagram does not coincide with the experimental one showing thereby that the mixtures deviate from ideal behaviour. The activity coefficients for each branch of the curve were determined as a function

Fig. 1. Phase diagram for naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene system: (I) melting point, (II) ideal curve and (III) thaw point.

of composition and temperature from equation (1). The values of $\Delta_f H_1^0$ (heat of fusion) were obtained from the literature. After computing $\ln \gamma_1^l$ and $\ln \gamma_2^l$ at x_1^l and x_2^l respectively and at the same temperature T , excess free energy (G^E) and excess entropy (S^E) were determined using equations (2) and (3) (Table 1),

$$G^E = RT(x_1^l \ln \gamma_1^l + x_2^l \ln \gamma_2^l) \quad (2)$$

$$S^E = -R(x_1^l \ln \gamma_1^l + x_2^l \ln \gamma_2^l) \quad (3)$$

TABLE 1—EXCESS THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS

<i>p</i> -Dichloro- benzene mole fraction	Temp (<i>T_m</i>) K	Experimental/(Ideal) values	
		<i>G^E</i> × 10 ³ kJ mol ⁻¹	<i>S^E</i> × 10 ⁴ kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
0.1	347.4	-09.39 (-82.12)	02.70 (23.64)
0.2	340.8	-18.73 (-141.87)	05.51 (41.63)
0.3	332.8	-27.36 (-169.16)	08.22 (50.83)
0.4	324.6	-34.21 (-181.58)	10.53 (55.94)
0.5	315.6	-38.19 (-181.94)	12.10 (57.65)
0.6	305.1	-38.23 (-170.67)	12.53 (55.94)
0.7	315.5	-33.34 (-160.36)	10.56 (50.83)
0.8	319.5	-23.03 (-133.00)	07.20 (41.63)
0.9	323.9	-07.97 (-76.56)	02.46 (23.64)

It is evident that the negative magnitude of *G^E* and positive magnitude of *S^E* values go on increasing as one component is added to the other. The magnitude of these values is maximum for the near-eutectic composition (i.e. 0.6 mole fraction of *p*-dichlorobenzene). The increase in *S^E* values indicates that the binary mixtures correspond to a state of higher probability than the pure components. A comparison of *G^E* and *S^E* values of a mixture with the values for ideal solution (obtained by putting $\gamma_1^1=1$ and $\gamma_2^1=1$ in equations (2) and (3)) gives useful information. It is observed that *G^E* values for all the mixtures are less negative than the corresponding values for ideal solutions, which indicates positive enthalpy values of mixing (*H^E*) for the binary solutions. The values also show that binary solutions are associated with higher vapour pressures as compared to for the ideal solutions. Since *G^E* values for all the mixtures are negative, the entropy factor (*T S^E*) overcomes the enthalpy factor (*H^E*).

Heterogeneous nucleation studies : The heterogeneous nucleation data are given in Table 2. It is important to note that although entropy of fusion (ΔS_m) values for naphthalene and *p*-dichlorobenzene are almost the same (53.1 and 54.7 kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ respectively) and that for the mixtures, these values should be higher by an amount contributed by the

TABLE 2—HETEROGENEOUS NUCLEATION DATA

<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene mole fraction	$\xi = T_c/T_m$	$\Delta T/T_m$
0.000 0	0.95	0.047
0.100 6	0.97	0.026
0.199 3	0.97	0.022
0.299 7	0.98	0.017
0.399 1	0.98	0.017
0.500 4	0.98	0.017
0.598 6	0.98	0.019
0.701 3	0.98	0.019
0.799 4	0.98	0.017
0.900 5	0.98	0.017
1.000 0	0.97	0.032

entropy of mixing, the ratio $\Delta T/T_m$ for pure components and the mixtures differ appreciably. However, the ratio *T_c/T_m* (crystallographic factor, ξ) has almost a constant value. ΔT is the undercooling (*T_m* - *T_c*), *T_m* the melting point and *T_c* the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation. It is observed that the ratio $\Delta T/T_m$ is maximum for naphthalene, while for the mixtures the values are much lower. The difference in $\Delta T/T_m$ values may be explained on the basis of difference in the viscosities of pure components. Our earlier studies⁸ revealed that the viscosities of pure naphthalene and *p*-dichlorobenzene are 0.9661 and 0.5903 cp respectively at 353 K. Since naphthalene is more viscous, the energy barrier for the transport of molecules to the growing cluster is higher and therefore nucleation is hindered. It therefore follows that a definite relationship exists between nucleation and the structure of the melt.

Linear velocity of crystallisation : The linear velocity of crystallisation (*v*) for the system plotted vs undercooling (ΔT), follows equation (4),

$$v = K (\Delta T)^n \tag{4}$$

where *K* and *n* are constants given in Table 3. The values of *n* are nearly 2 for most of the compositions and deviations from 2 may be due to differences in the bath temperatures and the temperatures of the growing interface⁹ which is expected to be large in eutectic and near eutectic compositions.

TABLE 3—LINEAR CRYSTALLISATION GROWTH PARAMETERS FOR VARIOUS COMPOSITIONS

<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene mole fraction	<i>K</i> × 10 ³ cm s ⁻¹ K ⁿ	<i>n</i>	<i>V</i> × 10 ³ for $\Delta T = 5$ K cm s ⁻¹
0.000	89.950 0	2.33	3548.00
0.200	1.047 0	2.22	177.80
0.400	0.501 2	1.90	42.66
0.500	0.002 8	3.50	7.08
0.611 (eutectic)	0.003 8	3.50	11.22
0.700	0.001 0	3.90	6.31
0.800	0.112 2	2.28	21.88
1.000	1.862 0	2.47	331.00

The theory⁸ which predicts *n*=2, assumes the growth to be due to the presence of repeatable steps caused by screw dislocations on the planar growing face and gives rate of growth by

$$v = \frac{3(\Delta S)^2 D (\Delta T)^2}{4\pi V_m R T \sigma} \tag{5}$$

where ΔS is the molar entropy of fusion, *D* the diffusion coefficient for transport across the interface, *V_m* the molar volume, *R* the gas constant, *T* the equilibrium temperature and σ the interfacial tension.

Table 3 reveals that for the same undercooling ($\Delta T=5$ K), there is a large decrease in the velocity of crystallisation when one component is gradually added to the other. But for the eutectic composition, an increase in the value of *V* has been observed. Similar results were observed by Parkhutik *et al.*¹⁰

as well. The reason for the fall in velocities of crystallisation for binary mixtures can be explained on the basis of change in the parameters of equation (5). V_m , R , T and σ are constants or have nearly the same values for pure melts and their mixtures but ΔS for the mixtures is larger than for the pure components. Therefore, the fall of growth rate for the mixtures must be dependent on D , i.e. diffusion. Diffusion is much hindered in viscous melts but the decrease in the viscosities of the mixture of the system as reported elsewhere⁸ does not explain the much greater fall in the velocities of crystallisation. The diffusion mechanism required to explain the kinetics of growth is discussed below.

In the crystallisation from melts of non-eutectic compositions at a given undercooling, fluctuations lead to the formation of a nucleus of a component (say component-1) having a greater concentration than the eutectic mixture. As this nucleus grows, the surrounding liquid becomes richer in component-2. The solid-liquid interface is surrounded by a layer called the diffusion layer which contains more of component-2. The growth of component-1 is guided by the diffusion of this component from the bulk liquid to the solid-liquid interface through the diffusion layer. For different melts, the thickness of this diffusion layer goes on increasing with the increase in concentration of component-2 till the eutectic composition is reached. Thus the progressive fall in the velocities of crystallisation when component-2 is added to component-1 (and vice versa) is explained. However, the situation in the melt of a eutectic composition is different. Here, the two components grow simultaneously, although one of the components is always ahead of the other. The diffusion of each component is facilitated by cross-diffusion and therefore a higher growth rate for the eutectic composition has been observed.

Microscopic studies : Microscopic studies confirm that the solid immediately separating out from a eutectic melt has an entirely different structure as compared to for the pure components. The crystal morphology of eutectic solid grown from melt is shown in Fig. 2. It is quite evident that the eutectic

Fig. 2. Microphotograph of eutectic mixture, unidirectionally grown at a rate of 5×10^{-3} cm s⁻¹; growth direction from bottom to top $\times 200$.

solid is heterogeneous and the two components can be seen side by side. It has a spherulitic growth form similar to the one observed in the crystallisation of organic high polymers from melts¹¹ and the crystallisation of Cr₇C₃ rods in an Fe-matrix¹².

Eutectic morphology can be studied in the light of classification proposed by Jackson and Hunt⁴ based on thermodynamic considerations. According to them, when both the components have $\alpha > 2$, where $\alpha = \xi S_m/R$ each face grows with a faceted solid-liquid interface and an irregular morphology of the eutectic is obtained. Since crystallographic factor, ξ is ≤ 1 , the $\Delta S_m/R$ values for naphthalene and *p*-dichlorobenzene are 6.40 and 6.58 respectively. The values are much greater than 2 and an irregular growth is to be expected. However, at moderate growth rates, the eutectic solid does not possess a completely irregular structure but has a quasi-regular structure. A eutectic microstructure (Fig. 2) has been solidified unidirectionally. The two favourably oriented spherulites have been elongated in the growth direction to give an aligned preferred crystallographic morphology.

In random solidification of eutectic melts, freezing may begin at a number of nucleation centres and each nucleus grows spherulitically until it impinges on the other growing spherulite (Fig. 3). It may also be noted that both the compounds, forming the eutectic, have pronounced growth rate anisotropy.

Fig. 3. Growth rate anisotropy of randomly grown eutectic mixture $\times 200$.

The formation of these microstructures is due to the simultaneous growth of two phases which is quite interdependent and cross-diffusion, ahead of the interface required to sustain the growth process. Neither phase can escape the influence of the other and the normal dendritic growth is prevented.

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